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Organisational Dynamic Capability And Corporate Resilience Of Food And Beverages Firms In Rivers State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined organisational dynamic capability and corporate resilience of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. The study was guided by three objectives with corresponding research questions and hypotheses. Correlation research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised of 161 managers and supervisors of 6 food and beverage organisations in Rivers State. No sample size was adopted for study considering the total population. Thus, the whole population served as the sample size. The instrument for the study was a questionnaire of two set, which was used to source data primarily. The instruments were validated and reliability coefficients of 0.82, 0.82, 0.81 and 0.73 for the four clusters: Sensing Capability (SEC), Learning Capability (LEC), Integrating Capability (INC) and Adaptability (ADY) respectively were established using Cronbach alpha statistics. Spearman Correlation was used to answer the research questions, as well as to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that, there is a strong and significant relationship between sensing capability, learning capability, integrating capability and corporate resilience of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. The study concluded that, organisational dynamic capability in terms of sensing capability, learning capability and integrating capability are critical key factors in enhancing corporate resilience of the food and beverage firms in Rivers State. Hence, it was recommended among others that, the management of the food and beverage should continue to imbibe effective sensing capability to promote their adaptability and enhance the firm's resilience. Also, the management of the food and beverage firms should continue to promote learning capability to enhance the firm's adaptability and hence fostering a high resilience in the firm.

Keywords: Organisation, Capability, Corporate Resilience, Sensing, Learning and Integrating

INTRODUCTION

The functionality of many companies many a time seem very uncertain. Recent Corona-Virus disease (Covid-19) pandemic has heightened degree of instability in commercial arena by paralyzing activities of various firms. Therefore, firms that wish to prosper in the long run need to be very robust. Akhigbe and Onuoha (2019) shared this perspective, arguing that in the face of rapid technological advancement and the inevitable collapse of certain businesses, only those with a high resilience capacity would be able to adapt and survive. Hence, an organization's resilience (i.e. its ability to rapidly recover from failures) is critical to its continued existence.

Organizational resilience allows for better crisis response, more adaptability, and the ability to deal with disruptive change (Jaja & Amah, 2014). Evenseth et al. (2022) define a resilient business as one that can anticipate and react to threats, bounce back fast from failures, and easily adapt to novel

situations. Seville et al. (2008) define business resilience as the ability to maintain operations and maybe even expand in the face of adversity. Jaja and Amah (2014) argue that companies cannot depend on being prepared for the worst; rather, they must constantly anticipate and adapt to new difficulties that may endanger the company's continuing success. When faced with both internal and external obstacles, a resilient organization may utilize proactive strategy to mitigate and even profit from the worst-case situations, as stated by Achebelema & Achebelema (2021).

Furthermore, given that no firm functions in a world devoid of chance events, there is always a need to strengthen their resilience in the face of adversity. Resilient organizations are the only ones that can survive catastrophic events including pandemics, natural catastrophes, terrorist attacks, human mistakes, and economic slump, as stated by Xio and Cao (2017). Given that numerous financially stable businesses in the past collapsed when faced with challenges, the above comment implies that a company's prosperity is no guarantee of its survival. Companies are constantly looking for methods to increase their profits, so it's critical that they develop strategies for dealing with the changes that undoubtedly will come their way. A company's ability to bounce back from adversity may be shown by how it handles a crisis. Increased productivity and a brighter financial future are only two of the many upsides of building a resilient business (Letam, 2020).

Resilience is an active and preventive coping mechanism that may help you weather the effects of change (Afifa&Santoso, 2022). A resilient company is one that can anticipate and respond to challenges, bounce back quickly and fully, and learn from its experiences (Hepfer & Lawrence, 2022). Letam (2020) outlines a number of metrics that may be used to evaluate an organization's resilience, including as situational awareness, adaptability, and vulnerability management. Three indices of company resilience were discovered by Hillmann and Guenther (2020): resilient behavior, resilient resources, and resilient skills. In contrast, we based our research on the business resilience measures of adaptation, agility, and robustness proposed by Annareui, Battistella, and Nonino (2019). Therefore, a firm's ability to respond rapidly to changing market circumstances is directly related to the efficiency with which it is structured.

According to Hermano and Martic-Cruz (2016), an organization's ability to be dynamic is directly correlated with its ability to generate performance, competitive advantage, and value. Organizational dynamic capability refers to an organization's potential to effectively mix internal and external skills via reconfiguration, as defined by Zhou et al. (2017). A company's ability to adjust to changing market conditions is vital to its continued existence in the face of competitive threats. Furthermore, Hsu and Wang (2012) said that companies' financial performance is affected by dynamic capabilities since they deal with the accumulation of various talents that are already incorporated into the business. Each business has its own dynamic capacity, which is based not on the quantity of workers but on the established systems and procedures. Particularly, a company's dynamic capability is essential to ensuring sustainable growth and adaptability in a complex work domain (Jibril, et al., 2018; Zahra, et al., 2021). This is because it helps guarantee that the organization's resources are managed in a manner that is consistent with the dynamism in the external environment.

The rising need to develop methods to boost organizational resilience has prompted a number of scholarly articles. Afifa and Santoso (2022) looked at how proactive risk research strategies may fortify a business. It was suggested that protecting oneself from harm may help one's resistance. Evenseth, Sydnese, and Gausdal (2022) investigated organizational learning to find out how it may help firms become more resilient. Organizational learning, they said, is crucial for a firm to build resilience. Akhigbe and Onuoha (2019) note that strategic agility inside an organization is crucial to bolstering the firm's resilience. Achebelema and Achebelema (2021) looked at how collaborative management and resilience go hand in hand. The organizational dynamic ability and corporate resilience of food and beverage firms in Rivers State, Nigeria, has not been the subject of much study. Even less is known about how a leader's skills might modulate the link between an organization's dynamic capability and its ability to weather setbacks. To address this knowledge vacuum, we examine the relationship between the organizational dynamic capability of food and drink firms and their corporate resilience in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The sudden economic downturn brought on by the COVID-19 pandemic has clearly disrupted preexisting business and production narratives, hence lowering the resilience of firms (Banjoko, et al., 2012). Companies that do not have the resources to withstand environmental disturbance are more likely to fail, which might dampen morale and consequently productivity. High competition, high manufacturing costs, a scarcity of raw resources, and a dependence on outmoded technology are all causing problems for companies in Nigeria, and beverage enterprises in particular, say Akhigbe and Onuoha (2019). Omhonria (2021) claims that food and beverage manufacturers in developing countries provide fewer options since they can't swiftly adjust to changing market conditions and customer preferences.

The food and beverage industry in Nigeria has not grown at all during the last decade, in contrast to businesses in other countries (Omhonria & Needorn, 2022). Over 900 Nigerian companies failed between 2000 and 2016, according to Abolo (2017). Onuba (2017) claims that a precipitous decline in Nigeria's manufacturing sector in 2016 significantly lowered the sector's contribution to GDP. There is no such thing as a problem-free business environment. However, the problem of inadequate resilience behaviour has further manifested in the limited adaptive ability of the organizations to respond to turbulent situations.

There have been several attempts to address the problem of these organizations' lack of resilience, but thus far none of them have succeeded. However, it is envisaged that by enhancing the organization's dynamic capabilities, the company's resilience would be strengthened. Success in the marketplace has been linked to a company's ability to adapt and innovate (Hermano & Martic-Cruz, 2016; Zhou et al., 2017; Zahra et al., 2021). This study tests the hypothesis that an organization's sensing competence, learning capacity, and integrating skill all play a role in its ability to withstand shocks and remain competitive in the food and beverage industry in Rivers state, Nigeria.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to examine the relationship between organisational dynamic capability and corporate resilience of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

1. ascertain the relationship between sensing capability and adaptability of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.
2. determine the relationship between learning capability and adaptability of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.
3. examine the relationship between integrating capability and adaptability of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between sensing capability and adaptability of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria?
2. What is the relationship between learning capability and adaptability of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria?
3. How does integrating capability relate with adaptability of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

This study is guided by the following hypotheses:

- Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between sensing capability and adaptability of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.
- Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between learning capability and adaptability of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.
- Ho₃: There is no significant relationship between integrating capability and adaptability of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Conceptual Clarifications

Organisational Dynamic Capability

Dynamic capabilities refer to a company's adaptability to use its resources efficiently to achieve harmony with its unique business environment (Rugami & Aosa, 2013). Additionally, the dynamic capabilities perspective shows how a company can develop new forms of competitive advantage by reviving its structure, competencies, and resources to achieve harmony with the dynamic business environment (Rugami & Aosa, 2013). According to Wheeler (2002), "firm processes that use resources, specifically the processes to integrate, reconfigure, gain, and release resources to match and even create market change" are considered dynamic capabilities. Additionally, according to Wang and Ahmed (2007), a company's dynamic capabilities are its "ability to constantly integrate, reconfigure, renew and recreate its resources and capabilities, and upgrade and reconstruct its core capabilities to adapt to changing competitive environments, in order to obtain and maintain competitive advantage." Additionally, dynamic capability was defined by Ofoegbu and Onuoha (2018) as "organisation's activities, procedures, and practices that enhance its competitiveness, thereby helping it to maintain a leading role in its industry." However, in this work, dynamic capabilities are defined as an organisation's ability to quickly identify areas that require change (sensing capability), design a suitable course of action, and implement it (reconfiguration capability).

Sensing Capability

A company's sensing capability is its capacity to identify environmental changes that could have an impact on its operations (Teece, 2007). It is accomplished by setting up procedures for routinely scanning both the nearby and remote business environments, interpreting information gathered, and filtering pertinent information (Teece, 2007). It entails identifying and keeping an eye on potential dangers and opportunities coming from both the internal and external environment. This study used measurements that were previously used in studies (Jansen, et al., 2005) as its benchmarks. When referring to the firm's scanning, filtering, monitoring, analysing, producing, learning, understanding, determining, and calibrating business possibilities and threats, Cao (2011) used a comparable dimension called sensing (shaping) opportunities and threats. This entails making a conscious effort to invest in on-going internal and external research to learn about consumer wants, technological changes and opportunities, supplier and competitor responses, and market structural evolution. The first acknowledged fundamental class involves scanning, generating, learning, and interpreting tasks and is called "sensing (and shaping) new opportunities." When prospects are first spotted, according to Teece (2007), "entrepreneurs and managers must determine how to interpret new events and development, which technologies to pursue, and which market segments to target." Businesses that grasp the potential frequently succeed in turning client needs into novel products (Teece, 2007). To make it work out, organisational processes must make sure that information is filtered and flows to the people able of making sense of it.

Learning Capability

Fang, Chang, and Chen (2011) opined that learning capability is defined as a firm's characteristics and managerial attributes geared toward the promotion and support of a learning process. It consists of the resources that the company needs to diagnose the need for employee training, evaluate ineffective business practices, and carry out the process of sharing information and knowledge gained among the staff. According to Santos-Vijande et al. (2012), learning capacity is a crucial resource that improves a company's productivity, inventiveness, and performance. The ability to learn helps company increase productivity, identify market opportunities, change business operations, reduce costs, and introduce new product delivery strategies to the market (Sok & O'Cass, 2011). It determines a small business's ability to compete, develop, and grow (Jerez-Gómez, Céspedes-Lorente, & Valle-Cabrera, 2005). A significant competitive advantage is created by SMEs firms that successfully establish and constantly improve their learning capabilities (Clements, 2010).

Integration Capability

According to Gewertz (2016), integration capability is the business structure competency that works to fully understand the organisational structure, connected assets, associations, and ideas between the connected assets and the business, as well as how the structure and benefits are operated. According to Teece (2007), integration can be defined as the participation of existing proficiencies into the company organisation, associating and integrating them with current assets and competencies. In

order to combine modern intellect with the contemporary brainpower cornerstone, integration calls for the bringing together of varied assets. This depends on internally advanced, mutually coherent intelligences, the acquisition of external assets, and the synthesis of available resources. A highly important component is dynamic capabilities since it helps maintain the change that intelligence formulation establishes (Verona and Ravasi, 2003). But only through combination or consolidation can intelligence become significant to the organisation (Ayuso, Rodriguez, and Ricart 2006; Verona and Ravasi 2003). According to commercial communication and collaboration norms, organisations used a variety of intellectual techniques (Macpherson, Jones, and Zhang 2004).

Corporate Resilience

Resilience is a theoretical idea, a metaphor, the outcome of human-environment interactions, a characteristic of a dynamic system, a quantifiable social and cultural construct (Mallak, 1998b), and a paradigm (Paton & Johnston, 2001). Although the origin of the term resilience is debatable, it can be linked to physics, psychology, or ecology (Manyena, 2006). Hollings' (1973) major book, *Resilience and Stability of Ecological Systems*, brought it to the field of ecology. According to Holling, resilience is "a measure of systems' persistence and their capacity to tolerate change and disturbance while maintaining the same relationships between populations or state variables." (Holling 1973). The capacity to rebound is another prominent definition of resilience (Coutu, 2002). The distinction between resilience in engineering and resilience in ecological is covered by Holling (1973). He claims that engineering resilience can be measured as the rate at which equilibrium is restored. He defines resilience in engineering as the stability of equilibrium close to a steady state. According to these perspectives, the word "resilience" can be defined as a term that suggests the capacity to adapt to both "normal" or predicted stresses and strains as well as unanticipated shocks and extraordinary demands. Organisational resilience is the ability of the company to anticipate potential negative events, resist by adapting to the threats, and recover by returning the organisation or state to a stable and acceptable state to the greatest extent possible (Burnard & Bhamra, 2011; Umoh et al., 2013). How prepared a company is for unexpected events may be reflected in their capacity to absorb shock through the creation of a resistance mechanism in the face of various disruptions that permeate the business environment (Umoh, 2007; Umoh et al., 2013). "The numerous concepts that emerge from definitions of organisational resilience include knowledge of the environment, level of preparation, the anticipation of perturbations," claim McManus et al. in their 2008 study. Similarly, organisational resilience is viewed by Annarelli and Nonino (2016) and Annarelli et al. (2020) as the firm's ability to survive shocks and unanticipated changes based on its strategic awareness and collaboration between internal and external capabilities. Despite the variety of resilience measures, adaptability is recognized and used in this study as the indicator of organisational resilience.

Adaptability

According to Walker et al. (2002), adaptability is a facet of resilience that stands for learning, the freedom to try new things and accept unconventional approaches, and the creation of generalized responses to a wide variety of challenges. An individual's or group's capacity or propensity to maintain an exploratory attitude toward fresh conditions as they develop and to respond to changing circumstances can be described as adaptability. The engagement and involvement of organisational staff in such a way that they are responsible, accountable, and preoccupied with developing the organisation's resilience through their work because they understand the connections between resilience and long-term success, according to Dalziell and McManus (2004), is what is meant by adaptability. An organisation's strategic plan, which focuses on identifying and developing key capabilities, resources, and other organisational processes in order to adjust to changing business requirements, is intimately tied to adaptability.

According to Starr et al. (2003), adaptability is the capacity of an organisation to change its "strategy, operations, management systems, governance structure, and decision-support capabilities" in order to endure perturbations and shocks. According to Olsson et al. (2004), adaptability is a characteristic of a socio-ecological system that enables it to deal with disruptions and changes while still maintaining crucial functions, formations, and feedback mechanisms. Similar to this, Adger (2003) claims that adaptability refers to a system's ability to evolve in order to accommodate perturbations or to expand the range of variability within which it can cope.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a cross-sectional survey research. The choice for a cross-sectional survey was because it allows us to get an instantaneous look at the outcomes and characteristics of the food and beverage companies. It is also useful for doing statistical assessments of the connections between different variables. Six food and refreshment organizations served as the population. Specifically, 161 managers and supervisors from six Rivers state food and beverage businesses that are members of the Food and Beverage Association of Nigeria (MAN). These organizations have been chosen since we they give a precise impression of our association and straightforward admittance to the information needed. Considering the population covered, sample size computation was pointless. Data were sourced primarily through Google structures, where respondents were given a URL to see poll and present their responses. Also, optional data were gathered from secondary sources which include books, diaries, and the web. The research instrument a questionnaire of two sets, which was responded to on a 4-point Likert-like scale, where 1 is the most grounded objection and 4 is the most grounded understanding. Somewhere in the range of 3 and 4, 3 demonstrates arrangement and 4 shows solid understanding. Also, for internal consistency steadfastness of the instrument, Cronbach Alpha reliability method was utilized to calculate the reliability coefficients, which yielded an index of 0.82, 0.82, 0.81 and 0.73 for Sensing Capability (SEC), Learning Capability (LEC), Integrating Capability (INC) and Adaptability (ADY) respectively. For data analysis, Spearman Correlation was adopted. Its statistics result from SPSS was used to answer both the research questions and to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. 161 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the respondents, but a total of 145 copies were retrieved, resulting in 91% retrieval rate.

RESULTS

The results of the analysed data for each research questions and its corresponding hypothesis are presented on tables.

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between sensing capability and adaptability of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria?*

Hypothesis (Ho₁): There is no significant relationship between sensing capability and adaptability of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Table 1: Sensing Capability and Adaptability

			Correlations	
			Sensing Capability	Adaptability
Spearman's rho	Sensing Capability	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.723**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	141	141
	Adaptability	Correlation Coefficient	.723**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	141	141

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Output on Research Data, 2024

To answer the research question 1, data on Table 1 produced a correlation coefficient, rho = 0.723 between sensing capability and adaptability; this value is high and positive, indicating that there is a strong relationship between sensing capability and adaptability of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

For hypothesis 1 tested, it was revealed from Table 1 that the correlation for hypothesis one shows a significant relationship between sensing capability and adaptability at $p < 0.05$ ($0.000 < 0.05$), rho = 0.723. We therefore reject the null hypothesis (Ho₁), and upheld the alternate hypothesis (Ha₁) thus, there is a significant relationship between sensing capability and adaptability of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Research Question 2: *What is the relationship between learning capability and adaptability of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria?*

Hypothesis (Ho₂): There is no significant relationship between learning capability and adaptability of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Table 2: Learning Capability and Adaptability

			Correlations	
			Learning Capability	Adaptability
Spearman's rho	Learning Capability	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.611**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	141	141
	Adaptability	Correlation Coefficient	.611**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	141	141

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Output on Research Data, 2024

To answer the research question 2, data on Table 2 produced a correlation coefficient, rho = 0.611 between sensing capability and adaptability; this value is high and positive, indicating that there is a strong relationship between learning capability and adaptability of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

For hypothesis 2 tested, it was revealed from Table 2 that the correlation for hypothesis two shows a significant relationship between learning capability and adaptability at $p < 0.05$ ($0.000 < 0.05$), rho = 0.723. We therefore reject the null hypothesis (Ho₂), and upheld the alternate hypothesis (Ha₂) thus, there is a significant relationship between learning capability and adaptability of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Research Question 3: *What is the relationship between integrating capability and adaptability of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria?*

Hypothesis (Ho₃): There is no significant relationship between integrating capability and adaptability of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Table 3: Integrating Capability and Adaptability

			Correlations	
			Integrating Capability	Adaptability
Spearman's rho	Integrating Capability	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.654**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	141	141
	Adaptability	Correlation Coefficient	.654**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	141	141

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Output on Research Data, 2024

To answer the research question 3, data on Table 3 produced a correlation coefficient, rho = 0.654 between sensing capability and adaptability; this value is high and positive, indicating that there is a strong relationship between integrating capability and adaptability of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

For hypothesis 3 tested, it was revealed from Table 3 that the correlation for hypothesis three shows a significant relationship between learning capability and adaptability at $p < 0.05$ ($0.000 < 0.05$), rho = 0.723. We therefore reject the null hypothesis (Ho₃), and upheld the alternate hypothesis (Ha₃) thus,

there is a significant relationship between integrating capability and adaptability of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Relationship between Sensing Capability and Adaptability

The first finding of the study between sensing capability and adaptability reveals a noteworthy relationship between the two variables. The Spearman correlation coefficient reveals that the p-value of 0.000 was less than 0.05 ($p=0.000<0.05$) which implies that sensing capability has a significant relationship with adaptability. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate hypothesis was accepted. The result of the correlation coefficient (r) is 0.723 reveals that there is a positive significant relationship between sensing capability and adaptability. Thus, enhancing sensing capability will help enhance adaptability. A coefficient of determination of 0.523 implies that 52.3% total variation in the adaptability of an organization is accounted for by sensing capability. Thus, the first objective of the study which sought to examine if sensing capability relates with adaptability was achieved. This finding agrees with that of Rehman and Saeed (2015) whose findings reveals that dynamic capabilities is related to the firms performance. These findings also conform with that of Yu, et al (2019) whose findings reveals that dynamism, disruption orientation, and resilience in the supply chain relates with financial performance.

Relationship between Learning capability and Adaptability

The second finding of the study between learning capability and adaptability reveals a significant relationship between the two variables. The Spearman Rank correlation coefficient reveals that the p-value of 0.000 was less than 0.05 ($p=0.000<0.05$) which implies that learning capability has a significant relationship with adaptability. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate hypothesis was accepted. The result of the correlation coefficient (r) is 0.611 reveals that there is a positive significant relationship between sensing capability and adaptability. Thus, enhancing sensing capability will help enhance adaptability. A coefficient of determination of 0.373 implies that 37.3% total variation in the adaptability of an organization is accounted for by learning capability. Thus, the third objective of the study which sought to examine if learning capability relates with adaptability was achieved. The findings agree with Kareem, and Alameer, (2019) conducted study on the impact of dynamic capabilities on organisational effectiveness and the results indicate that learning capability and reconfiguration capability have a positive impact on organisational effectiveness. It conforms with Nyachanchu, et al, (2017) whose study findings shows that the use of dynamic capabilities significantly impacts the firm performance.

Relationship between Integrating Capability and Adaptability

The third finding of the study between integrating capability and adaptability reveals a noteworthy relationship between the two variables. The Spearman Rank correlation coefficient reveals that the p-value of 0.000 was less than 0.05 ($p=0.000<0.05$) which implies that integrating capability has a significant relationship with adaptability. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate hypothesis was accepted. The result of the correlation coefficient (r) is 0.654 reveals that there is a positive significant relationship between integrating capability and Adaptability. Thus, enhancing integrating capability will help enhance adaptability. A coefficient of determination of 0.428 implies that 42.8% total variation in the adaptability of an organization is accounted for by integrating capability. Thus, the first objective of the study which sought to examine if integrating capability relates with adaptability was achieved. the findings agrees with Alfalla-Luque et al. (2015), Huo et al. (2014), and Zhao et al. (2013) whose study shows that internal integration has a favourable impact on operational performance. This finding conforms with Onyango, et al. (2015) whose findings reveals a significant relationship between organisational capabilities and performance of sugar companies in Kenya.

CONCLUSION

The resilience of organizations remains a critical factor in enhancing the sustainability of the establishment and it also help in boosting the fortune of the firm. Hence, maintaining a conducive organisational dynamic capability is a vital too in enhancing the resilience of the food and beverage firms. This study therefore concludes that, there is strong and significant relationship between

organisational dynamic capability and corporate resilience of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. In other words, organisational dynamic capability in terms of sensing capability, learning capability and integrating capability are critical key factors in enhancing corporate resilience of the food and beverage firms in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following are hereby recommended:

1. The management of the food and beverage should continue to imbibe effective sensing capability to promote their adaptability and thus enhance the firm's resilience.
2. The management of the food and beverage firms should continue to promote learning capability to enhance the firm's adaptability and hence fostering a high resilience in the firm.
3. The food and beverage firms should continually have a high integrating capability to boost the firm's adaptability.

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